

ISic3569

I.Sicily inscription 3569

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

natural rock

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Cava d'Ispica

Provenance

hypogeum, contrada Finocchiara, Cava d'Ispica

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Cava Ispica, contrada Finocchiara, hypogeum

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI337416

1. ΠΡΥΜΝΑ ΑΜΦΟ²crack in the rock² ΠΡΕ
2. Χ ΙΙΡ.
- 3.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645640

PHI 337416

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 54.0929.2

Rizzone, V.G., Sammito, A.M. 2005. Nuovi documenti epigrafici dal circondario di Modica. In Rizzo, F.P.(eds.), *Da abitato in abitato. In itinere fra le più antiche testimonianze cristiane degli Iblei*. Rome. pp. 45-62. At 51 fig.5-6

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